

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Abdrimov Inoyatbek Akhmedovich

Khorezm Academic Lyceum of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Deputy director for educational affairs

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Annotation: In this article, there are comments with theoretical foundations on revealing the psychological features of the development of creative thinking of elementary school students in the educational process. Discussions of researchers-scientists on the development of creative thinking are also presented.

Key words: Educational system, creativity, primary education, observation, comparison, analysis, heredity.

Introduction.

The problem of developing students' creative abilities is of special relevance and social importance. Today, the establishment of stable socio-economic relations in the country depends not only on the skills of specialists who are the managers of advanced scientific, technical and technological ideas, but also largely determined by the level of their creative thinking. At the current stage of the development of civilization, the need for active participation of Uzbekistan in the life of the world community has arisen. In order to rationally use the natural resources of our planet, issues of developing global projects, environmental problems, issues of space exploration and many other issues require the importance of integrating the system of general and professional education with the world system.

It is no coincidence that the modern philosophical and scientific idea about the structure and essence of scientific knowledge is significantly different from the traditional one. Today's science includes not only a set of facts, but also a set of cognitive-transformative processes that give it a real prognostic character.

Experts in the field of science, having studied the laws of the development of science, came to the conclusion that there are social procedures for the acquisition of scientific knowledge (in the broadest sense of the word): identifying new ones, processing them, structuring them, transforming them, etc. Further progress in the economic and social development of the world community is becoming increasingly dynamic and requires science.

A new approach to the structure of scientific knowledge, the interaction of science and production suggests the need for a qualitative revision of the nature of the educational process. Education is now seen as an active and creative, effective, intellectual interaction between the teacher and the students, as well as the students.

Today, systematic educational activities lead a child, a primary school student, to experience a sharp conflict between old habits of behavior and new living conditions. Before school, the main activity was games that required little and voluntary physical and intellectual effort from the child. Teaching required him to have systematic knowledge. As a result, he has

neoplasms in the psyche: social motives of educational activity are formed, the habit of systematic work is developed, the culture of mental and physical activity is nurtured, and the sense of responsibility is developed. The success of forming new qualities in a small person largely depends on how he prepares for school. The main directions of such preparation are: taking care of the general development of the child, educating his ability to control himself, developing motivations for learning.

In order to describe the topic of research, it is necessary to define the essence of the concepts of "creativity", "creative activity" and "creative thinking". The analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature on this problem revealed the following main directions describing these categories. This topic is relevant today, because the reputation of creativity in the whole world (especially abroad) has increased a lot recently. The development of scientific thought, the integration of science and production, the constant renewal of ideas and technologies - all this means creativity. According to the content analysis, the word "creativity" itself is one of the ten most frequently used words in pedagogy, psychology, sociology, philosophy, even political science.

Throughout centuries of history, mankind has sought ways to control the mysterious process of creation. The main conclusion reached by scientists in the last century was very hopeless for pedagogy: it is impossible to control the creative process, they were of the opinion that creative ability is a talent and talent is given to a person from birth.

However, the position of developing creativity is not as hopeless as it seems at first glance. Yes, creativity cannot be taught in the same way as standard actions and operations are taught. But everyone can develop and form creative abilities purposefully and consistently. Some develop this widely, while others do not develop well, but every child can develop a creative approach to activities.

Creativity is possible in any sphere of social relations of subjects. Creativity is a process that objectively or subjectively produces qualitative innovations. It focuses on new discovery¹.

Creativity refers to the ability to act in a problem situation, the ability to achieve a result without a model for achieving this result. This is the ability to see similar features in different phenomena and significant differences in very similar objects. This is the ability to transfer knowledge and experience to a new situation, ideas about the structure of the subject and its other functions, the ability to flexibly change the way of action in accordance with the task. Creativity is enriched and developed with the expansion of knowledge, skills, types and depth of problems and tasks to be solved. Development of creativity is an integral process of purposeful and comprehensive development and upbringing of a person.

The conditions for the development of creativity include: a creative environment and the attention of a creative teacher; ability to make positive creative decisions, tolerance, benevolence of others and independent, in-depth study of one's own capabilities.

Often, in the everyday mind, creativity is equated with various types of artistic activities, the ability to draw beautiful pictures, write poems, compose music. What exactly is creativity?

Attempts to understand and describe the phenomenon of creativity have been made by thinkers since ancient times (Plato, Socrates, Aristotle, etc.). Creativity is called by

¹ Веретенникова, Л.К. Подготовка будущих учителей к формированию творческого потенциала школьников [Текст]: диссертация ... доктора педагогических наук : 13.00.01 Количество страниц – 340 с.

philosophers "the cosmic principle of the world, the highest form of human activity" (I. Kant), "the essence of human existence" (K. Marx), "the enlightenment and transformation of the world" (N. A. Berdyaev). Modern research (V. S. Bybler, M. S. Kagan, etc.) allows us to define creativity as the highest and most complex form of human activity, which includes the activation of all the physical and spiritual forces of human experience, creates new things, and gives rise to originality and social- is distinguished by its historical uniqueness.

A great deal of experience in studying creativity was researched in Russian (*L. S. Vygotsky, Y. A. Ponomarev, P. M. Yakobson, A. M. Matyushkin, etc.*) and foreign (J. Guilford, E. Torrens, etc.) psychological and pedagogical studies. But despite this, in modern psychological and pedagogical science, the concepts of "creativity" are vaguely interpreted as the general ability of creativity. S. L. Rubinstein described creativity as an activity that creates something new, original, which later entered not only the creative person, but also the history of science and art². This definition of creativity is similar to the concept described in the dictionary of the Russian language by S. I. Ojegov, which describes it as the creation of new cultural and material values. In these interpretations, the essence of creativity is revealed due to such a feature as the novelty of a human-made product. However, characterizing creativity only by product innovation does not provide an understanding of nature and its mechanisms.

A more complete concept of creativity is formed in the dictionary of "psychology", which is also described as an activity that leads to the creation of new material and spiritual values. However, there is an important addition: creative activity means the presence of abilities, motives, abilities, which are distinguished by the individuality of the product. The above definitions describe not only the final result of creativity, but also the factors of its formation: abilities, motives, knowledge.

The full definition of creativity is given by the researcher Offered by Ya.A. Ponomarev. According to him, creativity "is a necessary condition for the development of matter, the formation and emergence of new forms of it, as well as the change of the forms of creativity itself. Human creativity is one of these forms."³

Currently, in the research of teachers and psychologists, an in-depth analysis of creativity, both in a broad sense and in creative activities in the educational process, is given. According to one, a distinction should be made between reproductive and creative thinking. In addition, the result of reproductive thinking is the creation of an object of activity based on existing knowledge, and the result of creative thinking is the creation of a new object of creation.

L. S. Vygotsky follows this point of view. He states that creativity exists as follows: *"..any human activity that creates new things, regardless of whether it is the creation of creative activity of something in the external world or a certain construction of consciousness or feeling that lives and discovers in the person himself"*.

A. V. Brushlitsky defines creativity as *"a process that leads a person to find something new that was previously unknown."* This position was taken by many researchers, in particular, A.

² Рубинштейн, С.Л. Основы общей психологии [Текст] / С.Л. Рубинштейн. - СПб. : Питер, 2000. - 712 с.

³ Пономарев Я.А. Психологическое моделирование научного творчества. — «Научное творчество». М., -1969. – 233 с.

Mateyko, who considered the essence of the creative process in repeating the existing experience and forming new combinations based on it.

According to the second view, the right of all thinking to be creative is the right of every human being to be creative. In such a position, B. P. Nikitin emphasizes that "our state, school, educators and parents have an increasingly important task: everyone needs not only a healthy and strong person, but also an initiative, thinking person, able to deal with any issue. they state the need for personnel capable of a creative approach, an active life position can be justified if a person thinks creatively and sees opportunities for improvement around him."

Also, B. P. Nikitin states: "... *the ability to observe, compare and analyze, combine, find connections and connections, features, etc.*"

N. A. Menchinskaya describes the following features of creative activity: "*the ability to change the methods of action widely, to subordinate the direction of search to the task, to cancel the accepted actions of thought, to flexibly change the methods of action according to the task.*"

I. Ya. Lerner defined it as "*a process of objectively or subjectively qualitatively new creation through specific intellectual procedures that cannot be conceived of as precisely defined and strictly regulated systems of operations or actions by man.*" Also, Lerner believes that the highest level of creativity is formed using creative thinking-effective teaching methods, because "*the procedures of creative activity are nothing more than the introduction of a person into possible activities that require the manifestation of certain creative characteristics and thereby form these characteristics. It is impossible to deliver with*"⁴.

The work of American researchers on the role of heredity in the development of a child's creative thinking is also interesting. E. Torrens, the creator of the creativity measurement system, says that heredity is not an important indicator of future creative productivity. The degree to which a child's creative impulses turn into a creative nature depends more on the educational and developmental process and the home environment. A family can develop or nullify a child's creativity at a young age.

According to the definition of S. G. Glukhova, "*creativity is a dynamic integral characteristic of a person, which is a necessary condition and result of creative activity, which determines the direction, readiness and ability of a person to express himself in creativity.*"

What is the internal content of the development of creative thinking, what is this development based on, what are its mechanisms?

The work of scientists shows that creative activity is the highest level of the educational process. But the principle of creativity, i.e. orientation to creative processes in pedagogy, to the formation of a creative personality, is currently insufficiently used in school.

Problems of creativity, development of creative thinking of elementary school students still remains one of the departments of "pedagogical problems". V. A. Sukhomlinsky named it that way in his time.

For many years, explanatory and illustrative teaching methods dominated the school, which is characterized by the presentation of knowledge in a ready-made form. Students' activities in this educational system include the development of skills and abilities to receive, understand, memorize and reproduce the received information. Thus, reflective thinking is emphasized and so-called productive or creative thinking is very little developed. Knowledge in such a system is scattered, piecemeal, and lacks an integrative approach to learning. What

⁴ Лернер И.Я. Проблемное обучение, - М.: Знание, 1974. - 184 с.

does not contribute to the multifaceted, full development of the mind, the creative thinking of the individual remains undisclosed.

This approach to education is very different from the needs of today's life. Of course, you need to provide primary school students with a knowledge system, teach the results of the achieved knowledge, but without a doubt, to develop creativity in the student, to educate an active, thinking, searching person, to make empirical findings, to determine the criteria for knowing life, it is important to be able to change and improve the world around and oneself.

Conclusion.

Summarizing the above, we can conclude that scientists do not have a consensus on the definition and content of the concept of "creative thinking", it does not exist at the moment. However, many researchers of this problem believe that everyone has the ability to be creative, and the task of modern education is to search for resources and opportunities that provide the development of creative thinking of every child during school education.

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